

Effect of quadriceps weakness on pain and impairment in osteoarthritic patients

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ABSTRACT

Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most prevalent form of arthritis and is associated with progressive physical impairment and psychological disorders such as anxiety and depression. To compare quadriceps muscle strength, knee pain, disability, and psychological status between individuals with knee osteoarthritis and healthy controls, and to examine the relationships among these variables. A comparative cross-sectional observational study was conducted across multiple healthcare facilities. Quadriceps muscle strength was assessed using Manual Muscle Testing (MMT), knee pain using the Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), disability using the Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index (WOMAC), and psychological status using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS). Independent-sample t-tests compared outcomes between OA and control groups, while Pearson correlation coefficients examined associations among variables ($\alpha < 0.05$). Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed between groups for knee pain, quadriceps strength, disability, anxiety, and depression. Knee pain showed significant positive correlations with disability, anxiety, and depression. A significant association was also observed between knee pain and quadriceps muscle strength, indicating altered neuromuscular function in individuals with OA. Knee osteoarthritis is associated with reduced quadriceps strength, increased pain, disability, and psychological distress. These findings highlight the need for integrated rehabilitation strategies addressing both physical and psychological components of OA.

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Introduction

The quadriceps muscles are an essential constituent of the body. These muscles play a crucial role in coordinating knee joint movements, influencing gait, mobility, and structural integrity. Meanwhile, the quadriceps muscle weakness can reduce the joint stability by degeneration of the knee joint cartilage, structural damage to the lateral and medial patellar femoral joint cartilage, bone marrow lesions, bone breakdown, joint enlargement, stiffness, and swelling (Alghadir et al., 2019; Rice et al., 2011; Segal & Glass, 2011). All these factors contribute to knee pain and compromised gait patterns, leading to osteoarthritis (Bennell et al., 2013). It is worth noting that a substantial number, approximately 27 million and 8.5 million, of adults in the United States and the United Kingdom, respectively, were diagnosed with osteoarthritis (Alghadir et al., 2019). However, the quadriceps weakness is a major concern in individuals with osteoarthritis, having a progressive impact on physical and mental health, i.e., anxiety and depression (de Zwart et al., 2018; Iyengar et al., 2013; Sharma et al., 2016; Wang & Ni, 2022; Zheng et al., 2022). It is rather complex to quantify the impact of osteoarthritis on mental health. It is divulge about 20% of osteoarthritis patients exacerbate the symptoms, including depression, which contributes to a diminished quality of life, increased utilization of healthcare resources, and a heightened risk of mortality (Iyengar et al., 2013; Rathbun et al., 2018; Sharma et al., 2016; Stubbs et al., 2016; Wang & Ni, 2022; Zheng et al., 2022). Thus, it is important to study the effect of osteoarthritis on physical and mental disability. And the aim of the study is to quantify the strength of the quadriceps muscles, knee pain, and the relationship among aforementioned factors and anxiety and depression.

Materials and Methods

A comparative cross-sectional observational study was conducted over a five-month period at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad, DHQ Hospital, Toba Tek Singh, and General Hospital, Faisalabad.

Participants

A total of **70 participants** were recruited and divided into two groups:

- **Osteoarthritis group (n = 35):** Individuals aged ≥ 40 years with a clinically confirmed diagnosis of knee osteoarthritis and current knee pain.
- **Control group (n = 35):** Age-matched individuals without knee pain or symptoms of osteoarthritis.

Participants with a history of knee surgery, neurological disorders, inflammatory arthritis, or other conditions affecting lower-limb function were excluded.

Outcome measures

Quadriceps muscle strength was evaluated using Manual Muscle Testing (MMT) conducted by trained clinicians. Knee pain intensity was quantified using the Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), scored from 0 to 100. Functional disability associated with knee osteoarthritis was assessed using the Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index (WOMAC). Psychological status, specifically symptoms of anxiety and depression, was measured using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS). (Dai et al., 2017; de Zwart et al., 2018; Ganu & Merchant, 2018; Niempoog et al., 2012; Regino et al., 2020). The ethical protocols were rigorously adhered to, and written authorization from hospitals and verbal consent were secured from the patients.

Data analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Independent-sample t-tests were used to compare outcome variables between the osteoarthritis and control groups. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to examine the relationships among knee pain, quadriceps muscle strength, disability, anxiety, and depression. Statistical significance was set at a p-value of less than 0.05. (Niempoog et al., 2012; Rosemann et al., 2007; Yang et al., 2011).

Results

Osteoarthritis is the most common form of arthritis, leading to physical deformity and psychological disorders such as anxiety and depression. This complex phenomenon is comprehensively explored in multiple hospital facilities by investigating two groups of patients, i.e., case and control groups. The two-sample independent t-test compared the variables of the case and control groups.

Two-sample independent t-test

The results of NRS revealed a highly significant difference ($t(df) = 55.959, p = .000, p < 0.05$) in scores between the Case Group ($M = 76.57, SD = 10.274$) and the Control Group ($M = 17.14, SD = 1.051$). The magnitude of the difference in means was substantial, with a mean difference of 59.429 (95% CI: 55.362 to 63.495). The results of MMT revealed a significant difference ($t(df) = 68, p = .000, p < 0.05$) between the Case Group ($M = 2.63, SD = 0.490$) and Control Group ($M = 4.43, SD = 0.502$). The mean difference of 1.800 (95% CI: 2.037 to 1.563) was statistically significant. Similarly, comparing the scores of Disability, a significant difference ($t(df) = 47.925, p = .000, p < 0.05$) was observed between the Case Group ($M = 59.54, SD = 11.049$) and Control Group ($M = 16.03, SD = 5.113$), with a substantial mean

difference of 43.514 (95% CI: 39.376 to 47.652). The analysis of Anxiety scores also showed a significant difference ($t(df) = 68, p = .000, p < 0.05$) between the Case Group ($M = 12.37, SD = 3.727$) and the Control Group ($M = 7.34, SD = 3.646$), with a notable mean difference of 5.029 (95% CI: 3.270 to 6.787). Lastly, in the case of Depression scores, there was a significant difference ($t(df) = 67.895, p = .000, p < 0.05$) between the Case Group ($M = 12.49, SD = 3.657$) and the Control Group ($M = 7.14, SD = 3.516$). The mean difference of 5.343 (95% CI: 3.632 to 7.054) was statistically significant. The aforementioned results indicate that the variables of the case and control groups differ significantly.

Table 1. Two-sample independent t-test for various variables of the case and control groups of patients

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		f	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
NRS	Equal variances assumed	12.921	0.001	29.278	68	0.000	59.429	2.030	55.378	63.479
	Equal variances not assumed			29.278	55.959	0.000	59.429	2.030	55.362	63.495
MMT	Equal variances assumed	0.869	0.354	15.175	68	0.000	1.800	0.119	2.037	1.563
	Equal variances not assumed			15.175	67.961	0.000	1.800	0.119	2.037	1.563
Disability	Equal variances assumed	13.584	0.000	21.145	68	0.000	43.514	2.058	39.408	47.621
	Equal variances not assumed			21.145	47.925	0.000	43.514	2.058	39.376	47.652
Anxiety	Equal variances assumed	0.128	0.722	5.706	68	0.000	5.029	0.881	3.270	6.787
	Equal variances not assumed			5.706	67.967	0.000	5.029	0.881	3.270	6.787
Depression	Equal variances assumed	0.216	0.644	6.231	68	0.000	5.343	0.858	3.632	7.054
	Equal variances not assumed			6.231	67.895	0.000	5.343	0.858	3.632	7.054

Pearson correlation

Pearson correlation of NRS and Depression

The statistical analysis revealed a substantial and statistically significant positive correlation between NRS and Depression scores ($r = 0.599$, $p < .001$). Specifically, the mean NRS score was 46.86 with a standard deviation of 31.093, while the mean Depression score was 9.81 with a standard deviation of 4.463. These findings strongly support that an increase in NRS scores is associated with an increase in Depression scores.

Pearson correlation of NRS and Anxiety

The statistical analysis unveiled a substantial and statistically significant positive correlation between NRS and Anxiety scores ($r = 0.600$, $p < .001$). Specifically, the mean NRS score was 46.86 with a standard deviation of 31.093, and the mean Anxiety score was 9.86 with a standard deviation of 4.450. The findings strongly support that an increase in NRS scores is associated with an increase in Anxiety scores.

Pearson correlation of NRS and MMT

The statistical analysis revealed a robust and highly significant correlation between NRS and MMT scores ($r = 0.812$, $p < .001$). Specifically, the mean NRS score was 46.86 with a standard deviation of 31.093, while the mean MMT score was 3.53 with a standard deviation of 1.032. These findings provide strong support that an increase in NRS scores is associated with a corresponding increase in MMT scores.

Pearson correlation of NRS and Disability

The statistical analysis revealed an extremely strong and statistically significant positive correlation between NRS and Disability scores ($r = 0.969$, $p < .001$). Specifically, the mean NRS score was 46.86 with a standard deviation of 31.093, and the mean Disability score was 37.79 with a standard deviation of 23.522. These findings provide robust support that an increase in NRS scores is associated with a concurrent increase in Disability scores.

Table 2. Pearson correlation NRS and depression

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
NRS	46.86	31.093	70
Depression	9.81	4.463	70
	Pearson Correlation	1	.599**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	66708.571	5739.143
	Covariance	966.791	83.176
	N	70	70

	Pearson Correlation	.599**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	
Depression	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	5739.143	1374.586
	Covariance	83.176	19.922
	N	70	70

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3. Pearson Correlation of NRS and Anxiety

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
NRS	46.86	31.093	70
Anxiety	9.86	4.450	70
Correlations		NRS	Anxiety
	Pearson Correlation	1	.600**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
NRS	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	66708.571	5728.571
	Covariance	966.791	83.023
	N	70	70
	Pearson Correlation	.600**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
Anxiety	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	5728.571	1366.571
	Covariance	83.023	19.805
	N	70	70

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4. Pearson correlation of NRS and MMT

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
NRS	46.86	31.093	70
MMT	3.53	1.032	70
Correlations		NRS	MMT
	Pearson Correlation	1	.812**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
NRS	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	66708.571	1796.286
	Covariance	966.791	26.033
	N	70	70
	Pearson Correlation	.812**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
MMT	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1796.286	73.443
	Covariance	26.033	1.064
	N	70	70

Table 5. Pearson correlation of NRS and Disability

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
NRS	46.86	31.093	70
Disability	37.79	23.522	70
Correlations		NRS	Disability

	Pearson Correlation	1	.969**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
NRS	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	66708.571	48892.857
	Covariance	966.791	708.592
	N	70	70
	Pearson Correlation	.969**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
Disability	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	48892.857	38175.786
	Covariance	708.592	553.272
	N	70	70

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

Osteoarthritis is the most prevalent form of arthritis. The gradual progression of arthritis leads to physical deformities and the emergence of psychological disorders. The comprehensive study unveiled the significant distinction between the quadriceps muscles, Knee pain, anxiety, and depression. Meanwhile, a robust positive correlation is found between knee pains and psychological disorders, i.e., anxiety and depression. In the context of the finding, it is found that the weakening of the Quadriceps muscles progressively diminishes the knee joint cartilage, bone degeneration, joint compartment enlargement, stiffness, swelling, and knee pain (Bennell et al., 2013). Thus, all aforementioned conditions collectively reduce the level of physical activity of an individual, leading to anxiety, depression, and eventually disability.

Conclusions

The study turned over the complex phenomenon of osteoarthritis and its effects on physical and psychological well-being. Osteoarthritis is the most common form of arthritis. The comprehensive exploration of this complex phenomenon highlighted a significant and statistically substantial distinction ($p < 0.05$) among the variables of the study encompassing NRS, MMT, Anxiety, Depression, and Disability. Furthermore, the study also unveiled a robust positive correlation between Knee pain and psychological disorders like Anxiety and Depression. The study's comprehensive findings emphasises on reaffirms the complex nature of osteoarthritis. It is also very important to adopt a holistic approach to address early intervention and rehabilitation, targeting Quadriceps muscle strength to mitigate the progression of knee pain and both the physical and psychological aspects of individuals with osteoarthritis.

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